

Conference Abstract

Dormice (Mammalia, Gliridae) in Ukraine: current state of knowledge and perspectives of investigations

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Abstract

I am setting up the national databases for four species of the Gliridae family (*Dryomys nitedula*, *Glis glis*, *Muscardinus avellanarius*, *Eliomys quercinus*) with data available from museum collections, scientific literature, biodiversity social networks, and original observations in nature made within the borders of Ukraine. The database contains 656 records: *Dryomys nitedula* 287 records, *Glis glis* 152 records, *Muscardinus avellanarius* 216 records and *Eliomys quercinus* 1 record. *Dryomys nitedula* is listed in the Red Lists of 5 administrative regions, *Glis glis* in the Red Lists of 2 administrative regions, and *Muscardinus avellanarius* in the Red Lists of 4 administrative regions. We revealed 2 findings of *Glis glis* outside the known range of this species. The current state of knowledge and distribution of Gliridae representatives in Ukraine are discussed. We propose to change the conservation status of the Garden Dormouse *Eliomys quercinus*, which is listed in the Red Data Book of Ukraine (2009) as a critically endangered species (a species on the edge of extinction). The revision of literature and museum samples attributed to this species has demonstrated that the only specimen, that without a doubt belongs to this species, collected in the Cherkasy region in 1965, was assigned to a non-existent settlement. The rest of the museum specimens (one from Ivan Franko National University of Lviv Zoological Museum and one from the National Museum of Natural History National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine) were redefined as *Dryomys nitedula*.

Keywords

Gliridae, distribution, population status, Ukraine

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